

DEVELOPMENT OF SOFTWARE ALGORITHMS FOR ENERGY-EFFICIENT CONTROL OF THYRISTOR SOFT STARTERS OF INDUCTION MOTORS FOR COMPRESSOR UNITS OF TASHKENT THERMAL POWER PLANT (TashTPP)

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Annotation: *The article discusses the possibility of implementing energy-efficient operating modes for the induction motor of compressor units at Tashkent Thermal Power Plant (TashTPP) with optimization based on the criteria of minimum losses, minimum stator current, and quasi-frequency control modes.*

Keywords: *energy-efficient control, thyristor soft starter, induction motor, compressor units, tashkent thermal power plant (tashtpp), software algorithms, tms320f2812 microcontroller, minimum losses, minimum stator current, quasi-frequency control*

Introduction.

The creation of software algorithms involves several stages of developing a complete digital control system for a thyristor soft starter of an induction motor, with final implementation based on the F2812 eZdsp microcontroller from the C2000 'Motor Control' series by Texas Instruments.

Currently, the drive technology market offers series of microprocessor-controlled soft starters from various manufacturers: MCD 3000 (Danfoss), Sirius 3RW44 (Siemens), PST (ABB), Altistart 48 (Schneider Electric), AC11 (Triol), etc. However, in most cases, regarding the organization of optimal control of an induction motor, the soft starter is only assigned the functions of organizing start and stop. The novelty and advantage of the proposed development lie in the creation of software algorithms within the TMS320F2812 microprocessor system for organizing energy-optimal control of induction electric drives with optimization based on the criteria of minimum losses and minimum stator current, both during start-stop and during operation.

As research methods at the initial stage, it is planned to use simulation modeling based on the Matlab software package and the Code Composer Studio 3.1

development environment, designed to work with the TMS320F2812 microprocessor from the C2000 Motor Control series by Texas Instruments (USA) [1]. To debug the microcontroller software and to finally verify the operability of the software algorithms, it is planned to conduct a series of experimental studies based on an experimental prototype of a soft starter with a thyristor voltage regulator and an induction motor.

Material and methods. The project results, in the form of ready-made software algorithms, create a real basis for the development of a series of devices based on thyristor voltage regulators, designed for energy-efficient control of induction electric drives. Features distinguishing the developed system from other devices of this class include the ability to implement energy-efficient control algorithms for induction motor operating modes with optimization based on the criteria of minimum losses or minimum stator current.

Figure 1 shows the functional diagram of a soft starter based on a thyristor voltage regulator with microcontroller control. The three-phase power supply voltage is applied to the power switches VS1-VS6 in the form of anti-parallel connected thyristors. The system state is monitored using power supply voltage sensors DV1-DV3 and current sensors DA1-DA3, which measure the current consumed by the induction motor IM. The necessary set of protective functions is implemented programmatically using information about the current operating parameters of the electric drive. The microcontroller control system generates pulse sequences that are applied to the control electrodes of the power switches VS1-VS6. Thus, it becomes possible to regulate the fundamental harmonic of the voltage applied to the stator windings of the induction motor.

Fig. 1. Functional diagram of a soft starter based on a thyristor voltage regulator with microcontroller control.

By using various laws for generating control pulses, it becomes possible to implement energy-efficient operating modes of the induction motor with optimization based on the criteria of minimum losses, minimum stator current, and quasi-frequency control modes. In this case, we are talking not only about the start-stop modes of the induction motor, but also about continuous operation modes, including those with variable load.

To ensure the required criteria for optimal control, in addition to the measured current and voltage values, information about the induction motor variables that are not directly measurable is required (torque on the motor shaft, magnetic state, and motor speed). This problem is solved using methods for estimating system variables based on measurements [2, 3], and the computational resources of the applied DSP processor are quite suitable for solving this problem.

Fig. 2 shows the functional diagram of the software organization for controlling a thyristor soft starter of an induction motor. Among all the tasks that need to be solved during the implementation of microcontroller control, it is necessary to specify individual modules, separating them by purpose and performed functions. In this case, the implementation of each task becomes available for individual improvement in order to increase the overall characteristics of the device, while individual settings allow changing the periodicity and priority of execution [4].

Fig. 2. Functional diagram of the software organization for controlling a thyristor soft starter of an induction motor.

In this case, the use of a real-time operating system is convenient for implementing system functions. Since we are using the TMS320F2812 digital signal processor [1], Texas Instruments offers a special application development technology, 'eXpressDSP', and a real-time operating system, 'DSP/BIOS', as software implementation tools [5].

The use of real-time operating system mechanisms allows for the simultaneous execution of multiple tasks with priority assignment and access control to memory resources.

The development results are presented as a finished software product, ready for use in creating new and modernizing existing digital control systems for thyristor soft starters for mass industrial induction electric drives.

Conclusion.

Due to the widespread use of induction electric drive systems in modern industry, it is essential to note the high economic impact in terms of saving electrical energy consumed by electric drives.

In conclusion, it is necessary to note that the development of the domestic drive technology market contributes to the displacement of products from foreign manufacturers and leads to the development of industry and the economy of Uzbekistan.

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